

Supplementary Material for RETRO-LI: Small-Scale Retrieval Augmented Generation Supporting Noisy Similarity Searches and Domain Shift Generalization

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Supplementary Material

A Datasets

We describe the dataset used in the language modeling experiments and the datasets used for the domain shift experiments. The goal was to use datasets with strong baselines to compare our model to, and which would need minimal pre-processing for our purposes.

A.1 WikiText

The WikiText dataset [20] was created to address the issue of there not being a text dataset with long-form content and original punctuation, capitalization, and numbers. As opposed to web-scraped content, the text is more structured and has fewer typos or colloquialisms. This is because the authors employed a measure of quality control by only considering Wikipedia articles, as well as restricting themselves to verified *good* or *featured* articles.

A *good* article has been nominated by a reviewer as well as confirmed by an impartial editor to be "well-written, contain factually accurate and verifiable information, are broad in coverage, neutral in point of view, stable, and illustrated, where possible, by relevant images with suitable copyright licenses."¹ Only about 0.5% of Wikipedia articles make the cut.

On the other hand, a *featured* article refers to one of the best articles on Wikipedia as decided upon by the editors. The criteria for a *featured* article are stricter than for a **good** article, and more comprehensive². Such articles make up around 0.09% of Wikipedia. More details on the processing steps can be found in Section 4.3 of their paper.

We use WikiText-103 which consists of around 103 million training and 254 thousand validation tokens. We use the same database for training and validation and generate it using WikiText-103-Train. Validation and training sequences of the WikiText dataset are disjoint by design. To avoid leakage during training we ensure that the neighbors of the training sequences are never direct continuations.

Finally, we report the 1-gram Jaccard-Similarity [21] of the training sequences and their two nearest neighbors in Figure 2 and the ten nearest neighbors in Figure 3 as a way to determine leakage. As is evident in the histograms, for most neighbors we do not get a Jaccard-Similarity of more than 0.2, so limited leakage is assured.

In the RETRO paper they checked if the training sequences have eight or more contiguous tokens in common with one of their neighbors to determine the degree of leakage. In our case, for the training and validation set, 4.76% and 5.1% of the ten nearest neighbors respectively have at least eight contiguous tokens in common with the sequence used to query the index. Evaluating such samples qualitatively, in Figure 1 we can show that this is hardly leakage in a sense that our model could exploit, as the neighbors come from different articles.

'frank headlam air vice marshal frank headlam, cb, cbe (15 july 1914 – 23 december 1976) was a senior commander in the royal australian air force (raaf). born and educated'	'alan charlesworth air vice marshal alan moorehouse charlesworth, cbe, afc (17 september 1903 – 21 september 1978) was a senior commander in the royal australian air force (raaf). born in tas'	'ray funnell air marshal raymond george (ray) funnell, ac (born 1 march 1935) is a retired senior commander of the royal australian air force (raaf). he served as chief of'
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Figure 1: Retrieval in action. (a) Extract of the chunk used to query the index (b) Closest neighbor in the retrieval database (c) Second closest neighbor in the retrieval database.

A.2 Domain shift datasets

For our domain shift experiments, we choose datasets of varying textual structures and sources. If a train/test/validation split is given, we take the training data to create the retrieval database and validation data to evaluate on. If only a train/test split is given, we use the test data to evaluate on.

Since for the inference experiments we created the retrieval database fully out of the training data and only predicted on the validation data, no leakage is possible.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Good_articles.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Featured_article_criteria.

Figure 2: One-gram Jaccard similarity of sequences and their two nearest neighbors (a) For WikiText-103-Train sequences (b) For WikiText-103-Validation sequences.

Figure 3: One-gram Jaccard similarity of sequences and their ten nearest neighbors (a) For WikiText-103-Train sequences (b) For WikiText-103-Validation sequences.

A.3 SlimPajama

RETRO was trained on MassiveText [23] which is unfortunately proprietary. Furthermore, The Pile [4] which is an open-source alternative to MassiveText and on which RETRO was also trained for comparison purposes, was taken down in July of 2023 due to a DMCA (Digital Millennium Copyright Act) notice³. The NVIDIA RETRO implementation training data was mostly based on The Pile [27] as well. This means that we could not use the same dataset as RETRO, which would make it harder for us to compare our performance to theirs. As an alternative, looking for datasets similar in data sources and size to The Pile, we decided on SlimPajama [28] which is a cleaned and de-duplicated version of RedPajama [3]. De-duplication is especially important for textual training data, see [16]. In Table 1 we compare The Pile to SlimPajama, where Pile-CC is comparable to CommonCrawl and C4 [24]. We see that although the data sources themselves are similar, the proportions are only somewhat comparable.

As most text in the SlimPajama dataset comes from CommonCrawl, it is largely unstructured and conversational. Although for humans it is easy to read and understand, this type of content is significantly dissimilar to Wikipedia articles, in flow, grammar, as well as vocabulary.

We use a sub-sampled version of Slimpajama-627B, namely Slimpajama-6B⁴. Furthermore, Slimpajama-6B still needed some clean-up, as there were many instances of repeating characters used as filler or for code comments in the CommonCrawl portion of the dataset. This leads to a total of 5.5B tokens usable for training. Finally, to reduce memory usage and simplify the code structure, we truncate all samples longer than 1024 tokens. Considering all of this as well as using their train/validation split, we end up with 2’886’850’140 training tokens and 4’948’252 validation tokens.

³ <https://academictorrents.com/details/0d366035664fdf51cfbe9f733953ba325776e667>.

⁴ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/DKYoon/SlimPajama-6B>.

Table 1: Dataset proportions SlimPajama and The Pile.

Data source	SlimPajama	The Pile
CommonCrawl	52.20%	0.00%
C4	26.70%	0.00%
Pile-CC	0.00%	18.11%
GitHub	5.20%	7.59%
Books	4.20%	12.07%
ArXiv	4.60%	8.96%
Wikipedia	3.80%	1.53%
StackExchange	3.30%	5.13%
Miscellaneous	0.00%	46.61%

A.4 *BBC-News*

The BBC-News dataset [6] consists of 2’225 documents from the British Broadcast Corporation news website, across topics such as business, entertainment, politics, sports, and tech. News articles are highly structured in terms of flow, grammar, and vocabulary, so this dataset is similar to WikiText in that regard. Using their train/test split and our tokenization scheme, we end up with 589’677 training tokens and 468’831 validation tokens. The validation set size is unusually large with respect to the training set size. Since we used the training set as our retrieval database, this might have hindered performance somewhat.

A.5 *Reuters*

The Reuters-21578 dataset as created and used by Hayes in [7], consists of 19’043 documents and has 674 categories in total. This dataset is comprised of news stories from the Reuters financial news-wire service in 1987 and just like the BBC-News dataset, is very similar to WikiText in terms of structure and language. However, the differences in vocabulary might be larger here, as the articles are from decades ago. Using Hayes’ train/test split and our tokenization scheme, we end up with 3’454’605 training tokens and 174’335 validation tokens.

A.6 *Pile-of-Law*

The Pile-of-Law dataset [8] was created in order to mitigate the effects of potentially harmful and biased training data such as can be found through web-crawling alone. The 34 data sources range from "legal case opinions and filings", mostly from the U.S.A., to study materials for law exams and were extensively analyzed for toxicity and biases. We use two of their data sources.

A.6.1 *Atticus Contracts*

The Atticus contracts subset contains contracts from the Atticus project, specifically the commercial contracts dataset [9]. It consists of 510 contracts and was created to train a model to highlight portions of the contract a human should review. Contract language is highly structured and repetitive, but not necessarily similar to Wikipedia or news articles. We now move away from *article* style text into something new entirely. Using their train/test split and our tokenization scheme, we end up with 456’681’888 training tokens and 152’337’169 validation tokens, which for performance reasons we had to sub-sample into 7’605’872 validation tokens.

A.6.2 *Founding Documents*

This subset consists of letters by U.S.A., founders, which were scraped from Founders Online [31] and consists of 137’883 training and 45’781 validation samples. Although this is in the Pile-of-Law dataset as well, it is not at all similar in structure to the Atticus contracts. Since these are letters, they are structurally more similar to articles than contracts, but as they are letters from the 1800s, the vocabulary and sentence structure are quite dissimilar to contemporary Wikipedia articles. Using their train/test split and our tokenization scheme, we end up with 55’818’926 training tokens and 18’605’985 validation tokens.

A.7 *OpenWebText*

The original WebText dataset used to train GPT-2 has not been released. However, as the authors have published how to re-create it, it has been repeatedly reconstructed. OpenWebText is created by taking the text of articles linked on Reddit⁵ which have at least 3 upvotes. We use [5], this version has over 8 million documents and no inherent train/test split. To keep the sizes manageable, we sub-sample 55% of the dataset to get 2’491’806’520 tokens which we split by taking 1% of it for validation. This is large enough to give us a good picture but not so large as to overwhelm the retrieval database size as in BBC-News. Overall we end up with 2’477’892’482 training tokens and 13’914’038 validation tokens. This is our second-largest retrieval database, right after SlimPajama-6B.

⁵ www.reddit.com.

A.8 CNN-DailyMail

The CNN-DailyMail dataset originally created in [10] for question answering, has been processed for summarization in [22], which is the version we use. Since these are again news articles, the text formality and structure are comparable to Reuters and BBC-News. Using their train/test split and our tokenization scheme, we end up with 223'216'223 training tokens and 10'116'369 validation tokens.

Table 2: Comparison of features among different dataset domains

	WikiText	BBC-News	Reuters	CNN-DailyMail	Atticus Contracts	Founding docs	Open-WebText	Slim-Pajama
Structured flow	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
Diverse Vocabulary			✓					
Higly formal					✓			
Historical						✓		
Less curated							✓	✓
Less formal								✓

B Background and Related Work

This is an extension of Section 4. In the main body of the work, only the three most important papers are chosen in order to adhere to the page limit. The papers presented here and their concepts were also crucial for this work and for possible future avenues to explore.

B.1 RAG

In natural language processing the branch of retrieval augmented generation has been gaining traction for a few years now. Given the tasks language models are expected to fulfill, from simple question answering, to fact-checking, to multi-turn conversations, combining a model's parametric memory with a non-parametric database is the natural next step. It builds upon an earlier idea of knowledge graphs [30] and enables not only a better understanding of our models' reasoning but also makes it easier to update knowledge. This is difficult at best and virtually impossible at worst with only parametric knowledge.

In the RAG paper [17] they did exactly that, where retrieval from the non-parametric memory is jointly learned with sequence generation. The neighbors are split into 100-word Wikipedia passages, as opposed to chunks. Just like RETRO, RAG computes cross-attention over the neighbors of tokens/sequences. Moreover, RAG's non-parametric memory only consists of a single Wikipedia dump (December 2018), as opposed to RETRO which has many data sources.

RAG set a new state-of-the-art on many open-domain QA tasks and even where they did not, they got close to the performance of more complex systems. Although since then there have been many systems that have outperformed RAG on open-domain QA, such as EDMR² [26] and FiD [12] which were specifically trained for QA. It must be said that RETRO does not outperform these models either. Though interestingly, NVIDIA's RETRO++, where they add the top-1 neighbor to the context, does outperform them.

B.2 SentenceTransformers

SentenceTransformers [25] is a Python framework for embeddings of images and text, specifically sentences. While BERT is a general encoder model, only trained for language modeling, SentenceTransformers (also called SBERT) is designed to generate embeddings for entire sentences. The purpose is to encode sentences and improve semantic similarity search.

It works by adding a simple pooling layer after the BERT embeddings. In this pooling layer word embeddings can be averaged, we can take the max embedding or we can take the embedding of the CLS token, which is used for classification.

In this paper, the authors use Siamese and triplet networks to train BERT. These neural network architectures are designed to learn embeddings for pairs or triplets of data points in a way that emphasizes their similarities and/or differences. Siamese networks have two subnetworks with shared weights. Each subnetwork takes as input a data point (in our case a sentence) and produces embeddings for those inputs. The objective is then to minimize the distance between similar pairs of inputs and maximize the distance between dissimilar pairs. Triplet networks work analogously, but with an anchor (A), a positive example (P), and a negative example (N). The objective is then to minimize the distance between the anchor and the positive example and maximize the distance between the anchor and the negative example. In the end, we obtain sentence embeddings that carry semantic meaning and can be compared using cosine-similarity.

The pre-trained model we use is called *multi-qa-mpnet-base-dot-v1* and is the best SentenceTransformers model for semantic similarity search. It was trained on question-answer pairs, which is the main use case for retrieval-augmented language models.

B.3 Self-RAG

Retrieval may not always be helpful and can in some cases be detrimental to the model's performance. In [1] they explored this question, where they retrieved passages on-demand, as opposed to indiscriminately retrieving a fixed number of neighbors like most retrieval systems do, such as our own.

This decision is made using *reflection tokens*, which allow the language model to critique its own output and decide if it needs retrieval to improve the factuality and overall quality of the generated text.

They evaluated their system on fact verification, multiple-choice reasoning, and a variety of question-answering datasets and setups. For these answers, they not only evaluated the exact match but considered fluency and precision/recall as well. They were able to show that their system outperformed other retrieval models on a majority of their tasks and datasets, achieving significant improvements in some cases.

This is an entirely new approach compared to how most RAG systems currently work. Through their evaluation on a diverse set of tasks, they have shown the need for and role of such reflection. We have observed similar issues in our experiments, so the next step would be to add such a self-reflection mechanism as well.

B.4 Chinchilla

In [11] they argue that most large language models are under-trained. The authors analyze the relationship between the number of parameters and training tokens given a fixed compute budget. Given two out of the compute budget, the number of model parameters, and the number of training tokens, they explain and validate through their experiments how to compute the third.

Due to our resource restrictions, we implemented the smallest RETRO model with 175M parameters. Considering Figure 2 in the Chinchilla paper, we can fix the number of parameters and estimate the number of FLOPs as $C = N \cdot D$ where D is the number of training tokens and N is the number of trainable parameters according to [14]. For RETRO-LI with WikiText-103 as both retrieval database and training data, $N = 120M$. We trained on 1'078'012 samples in total, for each sample we have 16 chunks, and for each chunk, we get 2 up to 10 neighbors, where each neighbor is 128 tokens long. This is 5.52×10^9 to 2.32×10^{10} tokens in total, so C is 3.97×10^{18} to 1.7×10^{18} . Even for only two neighbors, this puts us in the optimal model size range.

The non-parametric retrieval database helps with the Chinchilla law, as the retrieved neighbors increase the number of training tokens, alleviating the problem of under-trained large language models.

C Regularization

We present some details on the NEFTune noise regularization and as it pertains to the approximation to the hardware platform. The regularizer is added to the neighbor embeddings for the CCA blocks during training. For validation and inference, no noise is added to the neighbors, unless specified.

C.1 Ablation Results

For this set of experiments, we chose three neighbors and the SBERT word embedding model, which gave us the best results so far. Looking at the results for WikiText-103-Validation, we cannot see an improvement of perplexity in any combination of noise and noise placement when averaged over the random seeds, see Tables 5 to 7.

Table 3: Signal to noise ratio averaged over the WikiText-103-Validation word embeddings.

Noise type	SNR
Gauss, $\lambda_i = 0.4$	10.84
Gauss, $\lambda_i = 0.2$	45.16
Uniform, $\alpha = 5$	158.49
Uniform, $\alpha = 10$	39.62
Uniform, $\alpha = 15$	17.61

It is not entirely surprising that the generalization capability of the train to test set did not improve, as adding noise at train time can lead to the model effectively memorizing the noise [35].

The best combination for these experiments is setting $\alpha = 10$ and adding noise to the neighbors only, see Table 4. Adding noise to both, sequences and neighbors, see Table 7 gives worse results than adding noise only to the sequences. This suggests that the neighbors stabilize the negative effects of the noisy sequence. Furthermore, considering our best result comes from adding noise to the neighbors only, we can see that this NEFTune noise has a regularizing effect on the neighbors. This is likely due to the fact that our retrieval database is too small for our training set. In the original RETRO the retrieval database consisted of trillions of tokens and only saw improvement once the size of the retrieval database was in the order of billions, see the Figure on page 1 of the RETRO paper as well as the table on page 34.

As we show in Table 8, the checkpoints we trained with uniform noise and $\alpha = 10$ do not handle approximation to the hardware platform at inference time any better than the checkpoints trained without noise. Thus, uniform regularization does not play a role in this case.

Table 4: Perplexity results of NEFTune noise with alpha 5, 10, 15 added to sequence, neighbors, and both in RETRO-LI-on, three neighbors using SBERT embeddings, averaged over three random seeds.

Alpha	Sequence	Neighbors	Both
0	22.61	22.61	22.61
5	34.77	55.38	40.89
10	35.94	22.77	35.96
15	34.30	50.52	36.32

Table 5: Perplexity results of NEFTune noise added to the training sequence in RETRO-LI-on, three neighbors, SBERT embeddings.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
Alpha on Sequence	42	43	44	avg	Alpha on Sequence	42	43	44	avg
5	23.08	58.32	22.91	34.77	5	23.80	55.80	23.43	34.34
10	59.68	22.95	25.18	35.94	10	57.79	23.70	25.77	35.75
15	23.02	54.68	25.20	34.30	15	23.61	52.56	24.57	33.87

Table 6: NEFTune noise added to the neighbors in RETRO-LI-on, three neighbors, SBERT embeddings.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
Alpha on Neighbors	42	43	44	avg	Alpha on Neighbors	42	43	44	avg
5	22.23	85.07	58.83	55.38	5	22.73	79.83	61.45	54.67
10	25.62	21.18	21.52	22.77	10	26.39	21.63	22.11	23.38
15	23.96	60.31	67.30	50.52	15	24.57	59.17	63.12	48.95

Table 7: NEFTune noise added to both training sequence and neighbors in RETRO-LI-on, three neighbors, SBERT embeddings.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
Alpha on Both	42	43	44	avg	Alpha on Both	42	43	44	avg
5	21.70	22.80	78.16	40.89	5	22.28	23.34	72.95	39.52
10	23.69	60.72	23.47	35.96	10	24.25	59.01	24.04	35.77
15	25.01	61.31	22.65	36.32	15	25.62	58.26	23.27	35.72

Table 8: Perplexity results for the language modeling and the domain shift experiments, averaged over six random seeds. Models with various settings are evaluated: RETRO-LI-off and RETRO-LI-on (without neighbors, with ideal neighbors, and with noisy neighbors impacted by $\lambda_i \in \{0.2, 0.4, 1\}$).

Retrieval	Settings	Regularizer	WikiText	BBC-News	Reuters	Founding docs	CNN-DailyMail	Atticus contracts	Open-WebText	Slim-Pajama
off	Normal inf.	None	20.62	130.31	168.91	266.85	171.56	329.98	312.15	489.46
On	No neighbors	None	19.74	129.63	157.30	265.53	170.43	322.67	306.10	485.84
		Uniform, $\alpha = 10$	19.71	130.51	157.79	265.96	170.51	324.63	308.61	491.11
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.2$	19.72	129.17	155.05	260.16	168.78	318.37	301.94	481.10
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.4$	19.71	130.38	157.47	268.32	170.78	327.63	309.84	504.20
	Ideal retrieval	None	19.60	127.82	154.73	260.63	167.21	316.48	299.81	475.23
		Uniform, $\alpha = 10$	19.60	127.84	154.73	260.23	167.26	318.01	300.87	477.70
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.2$	19.60	127.73	153.16	258.27	166.25	314.28	297.08	472.87
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.4$	19.63	128.10	154.57	261.70	167.32	317.94	302.20	477.42
	Noisy retrieval, $\lambda_i = 0.2$	None	19.60	127.86	154.75	260.68	167.24	316.54	299.88	475.36
		Uniform, $\alpha = 10$	19.60	127.88	154.76	260.26	167.30	318.17	300.99	477.79
		Gaussian, $\lambda = 0.2$	19.60	127.75	153.18	258.34	166.27	314.35	297.18	473.02
	Noisy retrieval, $\lambda_i = 0.4$	Gaussian, $\lambda = 0.4$	19.63	128.13	154.62	261.80	167.35	318.06	302.33	477.71
		None	19.61	127.94	154.84	260.86	167.35	316.83	300.10	475.76
		Uniform, $\alpha = 10$	19.61	127.97	154.87	260.41	167.37	318.39	301.24	478.18
	Noisy retrieval, $\lambda_i = 1.0$	Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.2$	19.60	127.83	153.31	258.58	166.35	314.60	297.47	473.45
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.4$	19.63	128.30	154.81	262.11	167.46	318.44	302.76	478.73
		None	19.66	128.49	155.54	261.92	168.53	318.66	301.63	478.18
		Uniform, $\alpha = 10$	19.64	128.85	155.94	262.07	168.17	321.32	303.92	482.51
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.2$	19.63	128.36	154.06	259.88	166.87	316.00	299.16	475.97
		Gaussian, $\lambda_t = 0.4$	19.68	129.42	156.42	265.03	168.69	322.21	306.40	504.20

It is clear in Table 8 and Figures 4 that not only is *Gaussian*, $\lambda_t = 0.2$ the best checkpoint overall it can handle large amounts of noise better than other regularizers or no regularizer. We see how for $\lambda_i = 0.2$ and $\lambda_i = 0.4$ the perplexity barely increases for any of the regularizers (None, Uniform, Gaussian). For $\lambda_i = 1.0$ which is the largest relative standard deviation in our setup this changes. Here clear patterns emerge. For instance, *Gaussian*, $\lambda_t = 0.4$ does consistently worst because it has the lowest signal-to-noise ratio of the regularizers shown here. It is most affected by $\lambda_i = 1.0$. Moreover, *Gaussian*, $\lambda_t = 0.2$ does best for every dataset and noise level at inference time. It is least affected by $\lambda_i = 1.0$. This is unsurprising, as we also observe that out of all the regularizers *Gaussian*, $\lambda_t = 0.2$ is least affected by the inference mode *no retrieval*. Most of this model’s generalization performance comes from improved language modeling and not from the retrieved neighbors themselves.

The *uniform regularizer* and *no regularizer* get similar results for almost all combinations of datasets and types of inference noise, but that changes for $\lambda_i = 1.0$. For all datasets except BBC-News and WikiText-103, *no regularizer* is less affected by $\lambda_i = 1.0$ than the *uniform regularizer*. However, it has to be said that, even for these two datasets, the performance decrease is very similar.

Figure 4: Perplexity evolution with increased inference noise for all datasets.

D Perplexity Discussion

Perplexity is a performance measure in natural language processing (NLP) used to evaluate how well a model predicts a sample. It quantifies how a probability distribution or language model represents the data it is trained on. A lower perplexity score indicates that the model is more accurate and has a better understanding of the data. The model is essentially less surprised by the next word it sees, hence the name. In language modeling, perplexity is the exponential of the cross-entropy loss. In NLP we usually use the exponent base as opposed to base 2 but both are acceptable.

The state-of-the-art language modeling perplexity of 2.4 on WikiText-103-Test is achieved by the RETRO model⁶, with a large gap to the second best perplexity of 10.6. As already discussed, advancements of perplexity on WikiText-103 are usually due to dataset leakage. Most if not all large language models train on some snapshot of English Wikipedia. With the emergence of foundational models, it is nearly impossible to avoid validation/test set leakage.

Perplexity has other issues as well. As it is a manner of evaluating the probability distribution, it cannot handle words with zero probability, so out of vocabulary words. Language models with a closed vocabulary will have lower perplexity than those with an open vocabulary, which assign probabilities to all words, if need be down to the characters. Finally, it is difficult to compare perplexities between closed vocabulary tokenizers, due to the size of the vocabularies. A larger vocabulary can lead to higher perplexities, as there are more words to consider for the next word.

Despite these issues, perplexity is used as a performance measure due to its simplicity and comparability. In NLP we are aware of these issues and attempt to alleviate them by using closed vocabularies of similar sizes, when our goal is to present and compare perplexities. Furthermore, it is difficult to find a quantitative measure for language models. The BLEU or ROUGE score, *Word error rate*, or *Character error rate* all depend on generating text. Generation is already the next step which is subject to hyperparameter-tuning and post-processing. Not to mention, that the goal might not be to generate the exact continuation, as depending on the use-case, semantically similar output should be accepted as well. To compare the output of the language model directly, we must use a measure that does not sample but evaluates the probability distributions directly.

Recently, bits-per-byte is used in order to measure the performance of a language model. Bits-per-byte refers to data storage efficiency, it describes a compression ratio. The idea behind it is the same as behind perplexity, where $bpb = 0$ means that the model knows exactly what symbol will be next whereas $bpb = \log_2(\text{vocab_size})$ means the model needs to be given the next symbol exactly. It is related to perplexity in the sense that cross-entropy loss for a character-level language model averaged over a dataset is bits-per-character. It is computed as $L \times \log_2(e)$ where L is the loss and is a loss-based performance measure. As it also highly depends on the vocabulary size, it is not a more general measure than perplexity.

D.1 Full Results

Here we present the full result tables, for each random seed and all number of neighbors. Variations across random seeds are likely due to the fact that we have to fix the number of training steps. We do not stop once we overfit, as we do not reach that stage with most of our experiments. For full transparency, we present both, the perplexity of the sliding window approach (as RETRO computes it) and the full results (simply $\exp(\text{loss})$).

D.1.1 Embeddings

We see strong variations across random seeds, suggesting that our system is sensitive to the initial samples and gets stuck in local minima quickly. Moreover, as we do not observe this behavior for SBERT embeddings, we can conclude that this is due to less-than-ideal neighbors, which strongly impact the system, especially in the beginning. It has to be said that even RETRO-Off has one particularly bad seed, which suggests that at least part of the reason we get stuck in local minima is due to the loss landscape itself.

Finally, note how not all checkpoints improve upon utilizing the sliding window approach. This suggests that this approach is better suited for demonstrating the performance of a language model. If the performance decreases given 75% of the context, the model is truly unsuited for the task.

Table 9: Perplexity results of experiments for RETRO-LI-on/-off with BERT embeddings on a variety of number of neighbors and random seeds.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
BERT	42	43	44	avg	BERT	42	43	44	avg
2	25.51	61.17	65.11	50.59	2	26.39	61.28	66.10	51.26
3	54.61	56.90	23.29	44.93	3	52.67	53.91	23.77	43.45
5	24.24	22.67	39.85	28.92	5	24.74	23.23	39.87	29.28
7	26.35	60.96	60.02	49.11	7	27.09	58.97	58.75	48.27
10	23.48	60.21	63.62	49.10	10	24.10	57.01	61.41	47.51
RETRO-LI-Off	55.56	21.60	22.02	32.06	RETRO-LI-Off	53.17	22.21	22.59	32.66

⁶ <https://paperswithcode.com/sota/language-modelling-on-wikitext-103>.

Table 10: Perplexity results of experiments for RETRO-LI-on/-off with SBERT embeddings on a variety of number of neighbors and random seeds.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
SBERT	42	43	44	avg	SBERT	42	43	44	avg
2	24.26	24.07	23.82	24.05	2	24.95	24.84	24.39	24.73
3	21.35	24.59	21.89	22.61	3	22.05	25.01	22.52	23.19
5	24.66	21.83	58.84	35.11	5	25.42	22.82	65.00	37.75
7	22.77	25.39	54.09	34.08	7	23.43	26.10	56.32	35.28
10	21.49	24.26	23.97	23.24	10	22.10	25.05	24.80	23.98
RETRO-LI-Off	55.56	21.60	22.02	32.06	RETRO-LI-Off	53.17	22.21	22.59	32.66

E Implementing RETRO

In this section, we provide additional details on the architecture introduced in Section 2. Specifically, we elaborate on other changes we made to the RETRO architecture and how we implemented them.

E.1 RETRO-fitted GPT-2

One contribution of the RETRO paper is that this type of architecture is straightforward to apply to other language models. This is called RETRO-fitting. This is beneficial and efficient, as it allows us to leverage pre-trained models and augment them with retrieval capabilities. To do so, we must be able to access each attention block separately, as the chunked cross-attention blocks are added to every third layer starting from the sixth (or ninth for larger models). These attention blocks can then be frozen.

This reduces the number of trainable parameters, making it faster to train. In the paper, instead of taking a pre-trained GPT-2 checkpoint, the authors built a GPT-2-like model with the appropriately changed parameters (see Table 11) . Then they trained it without retrieval before RETRO-fitting it. Due to our limited resources, we use the publicly available GPT-2 checkpoints. Consequently, we had to change the aforementioned hyperparameters. Moreover, we had to train additional feed-forward network parameters at the end of the attention layers. Using a pre-trained model leads to a significant improvement of perplexity on the language modeling task compared to training RETRO from scratch and it decreases our model size by 30%.

For later experiments, we use our trained RETRO-LI-off with GPT-2 attention blocks as a checkpoint. This enables us to freeze all decoder layers except the CCA, just as in the original paper. Additionally, it decreases the number of trainable parameters even further from the complete RETRO-LI by 90.29%. The architecture is visualized in Diagram 5.

Note that RETRO differentiates between the baseline transformer, which is their GPT-2-like model, and RETRO-off, which is their RETRO-on without CCA. However, they repeatedly demonstrated that their performances are almost identical. In our work, we had no baseline transformer. We compare the RETRO architecture with and without CCA.

Table 11: Changes to the hyperparameters for RETRO-fitting.

Hyperparameter	GPT-2	RETRO
d_model	896	768
d_ff	3584	3072
# attention heads	12	16
vocabulary size	50'257	8'000 ⁷

E.2 Changes

Most changes are made in order to adapt the RETRO architecture to the GPT-2 attention blocks.

E.2.1 Index

FAISS is an open-source library for similarity search created by Facebook Research. Through clustering and quantization, it efficiently searches billions of vectors in milliseconds. Although RETRO used ScaNN for their purposes, we chose FAISS due to its ease of use and its parallelization abilities.

FAISS has several hyperparameters that must be set following the size of the database. According to their own recommendation, the number of centroids⁸ should be set as about \sqrt{n} where n is the number of index entries, in our case this refers to the number of chunks. For WikiText-103 this ends up being around 1024, for SlimPajama-6B and OpenWebText, this is around 4096. The number of inverted lists to be searched at query time can be set freely. NVIDIA's Megatron RETRO implementation set it as 0.1% of the inverted lists, whereas we stick to $\sqrt{n_{centroids}}$.

⁷ The vocabulary size of the original RETRO is 128'000, but our training data is much smaller thus we chose an appropriately smaller vocabulary size.

⁸ Also called inverted lists.

Figure 5: Number of trainable (violet) and frozen (blue) parameters in the (a) RETRO architecture and (b) RETRO-fitted GPT-2 architecture.

Table 12: Input and output dimensions for the blocks in the RETRO architecture.

Block	Input	Output
Sentence-Transformer	[chunk_len]	[d_model]
GPT-2 Embedding	[seq_len]	[seq_len, d_model]
GPT-2 Attention	[seq_len, d_model]	[seq_len, d_model]
CCA	[seq_len, d_model], [n_chunks, n_neighbors, neighbor_len, d_model]	[n_chunks, n_neighbors, neighbor_len, d_model]
FFW	[seq_len, d_model]	[seq_len, d_model]
READ	[n_embed]	[d_model, vocab_size]
Nearest Neighbor Encoder	[seq_len, d_model], [n_chunks, n_neighbors, neighbor_len, d_model]	[n_chunks, n_neighbors, neighbor_len, d_model]
Normalizer	[n_chunks, n_neighbors, neighbor_len, d_model]	[n_chunks, n_neighbors, neighbor_len, d_model]

Creating the Index The workflow begins with the raw text files chosen for the retrieval database. We tokenize the text using the GPT-2 tokenizer. This first tokenization is only used to divide the text into chunks of length 64. To add them to the index, we de-tokenize the chunks, and re-tokenize them using BERT / SBERT, so we can embed them using these models. We prefer them over GPT-2 embeddings as they more effectively capture the semantic meaning. These chunk embeddings are then added to the FAISS index as keys, with their continuations (the next 64 tokens) as values.

Before we tokenize with GPT-2, we normalize the text using the BERT normalizer. This is essential, as BERT and GPT treat neither special characters nor repeated characters the same way. Without normalization, the re-tokenized chunk might be longer than 512 tokens. The pseudo-code for this algorithm is in Algorithm 1 in detail.

Algorithm 1 Creating the index.

```

index ← IndexIVFPQ()
X ← INPUT TEXT
Xnorm ← bert_normalizer(X)
Xtokenized ← GPT2_tokenizer(Xnorm)
chunks ← split_in_chunks(Xtokenized)
chunkstext ← [GPT2_tokenizer.decode(c) for c in chunks]
chunksemb ← [SBert_embedding(c) for c in chunkstext]
index ← index.add(chunksemb)

```

IVFPQ⁹ refers to an inverted file with product quantizer. The vectors are clustered and an inverted list for these clusters is created.

Algorithm 2 Creating the training data.

```

X ← INPUT TEXT
Xnorm ← bert_normalizer(X)
Xtokenized ← GPT2_tokenizer(Xnorm)
for i = 0; i < len(Xtokenized); i = i + 1024 do
  src ← seq[i : i + 1024]
  tgt ← seq[i + 1 : i + 1025]
  chunks ← split_in_chunks(src)
  for c in chunks do
    ctext ← GPT2_tokenizer.decode(c)
    cemb ← SBert_embedding(c)
    neighbors, distances ← index.search(cemb)
    save(src, neighbors, distances, tgt)
  end for
end for

```

⁹ https://faiss.ai/cpp_api/struct/structfaiss_1_1IndexIVFPQ.html.

Getting the nearest neighbors To make training more efficient, for each training sequence, we get the ten nearest neighbors for each chunk offline. We save them and their associated distance matrices to be loaded during training. In the first step, we again normalize using the BERT normalizer and tokenize using the GPT-2 tokenizer. Then we go through the entire tokenized text in steps of 1024 (our sequence length). Each sequence is split into chunks of length 64, which are used to query the index for their top k neighbors of each chunk. Once found, we save not only the source sequence, the nearest neighbors for all 16 chunks, and their distance matrices but also the target sequence, which is the source sequence shifted by one token.

The distance matrices are not strictly necessary for our training setup and can be excluded. In our case, we kept them in order to analyze if adding noise to the distance matrix, thus shuffling the top 10 neighbors, then taking the new top k neighbors would significantly impact the performance. The goal of this experiment was to argue that saving these neighbors on specialized hardware with inherent noise is still feasible. It turned out that our system is even more robust, where we can not only shuffle the neighbors but also add noise to the neighbor embeddings themselves without significant performance degradation.

E.2.2 Minor Changes

Positional Embeddings The positional encodings were ablated in the paper, and Figure 8 shows minimal relevance to the choice of it. Thus, we instead use the state-of-the-art rotary positional embeddings [29]. They work by using rotational operations to capture positional information. Specifically, they rotate the embeddings based on the position in the sequence. These rotations are learnable and can be reversed.

Sequence Length We use GPT-2 attention blocks, meaning the input sequence must be of length 1024. In the original paper, the chunk length was 64 tokens and the sequence length was 2048 tokens, neither of which is justified or ablated. As such, to have the input of the correct shape, we reduce the number of chunks per sequence to 16 as opposed to 32, whereas the chunk length remains unchanged.

Optimizer and Batch Size RETRO itself used AdamW [19], so Adam [15] with true weight decay (as opposed to Adam with L2 regularization), and a linearly increasing learning rate schedule with a batch size of 256 for their smallest model. Due to our memory restrictions, we can work with a batch size of 2 at most. Thus, using the same hyperparameters as Table 11 in [2] does not yield the same results in terms of convergence. As a consequence, we tried a variety of optimizers and decided on RAdam [18], which has the additional benefit of eliminating the need for us to tune the hyperparameters.

RAdam works by regularizing the variance of the gradients, leading to more stable training, especially in the beginning where the variance might be particularly large. Note that what is displayed as "noam" in the figure, refers to the optimizer used in the original transformer paper [33], where we have Adam with linear warmup and a learning rate schedule that decays the learning rate proportional to the inverse square root of the step number.

Figure 6: Comparison of various optimizers on WikiText-103.

E.3 Previous Implementations

NVIDIA’s Megatron project already has a working version of RETRO [34], but everything from the creation of the search database to the training is based on having much more resources than we do. Moreover, as it is part of a larger project, even following the code flow is difficult, let alone adding changes for this work. Due to these reasons, we chose not to move forward with this implementation of RETRO. Although we kept the implementation as a reference to check our architectural decisions against.

As a basis for our experiments, we used the smaller and easier-to-work-with "labml" [32] implementation of RETRO to build our code on. Although only meant as a tutorial to better understand the chunked cross-attention and retrieval mechanism, it has such a clean and simple structure that adding to it for our needs was straightforward. Many changes to this code base were necessary, most importantly to the database, dataset creation, and the training loop, as well as adding RETRO-fitted GPT-2. Still, having this framework to start with was hugely beneficial.

F Additional Ablations

Most of our ablations concern the retrieval aspect of the system. Here we explore the language model itself. We wanted to see if it would be possible to fine-tune the GPT-2 attention blocks as well, in order to improve performance even further. It did not, which makes the case for using foundational models stronger.

F.1 GPT-2 unfreeze

We kept the GPT-2 backbone frozen for most experiments but did one ablation where we (1) Unfroze GPT-2 and continued to train on one of the pre-trained checkpoints (denoted *from ckp*), (2) Trained from scratch by keeping the GPT-2 parameters trainable (denoted *from scratch*). This increases the number of trainable parameters, which consequently increases the training time.

Considering the results in Table 13, we observe that unfreezing GPT-2 and continuing to train from a previous checkpoint does improve our performance slightly for the RETRO-LI-off case. It is clear, however, that this was due to there no longer being one significant outlier (random seed 42). So it is a stabilizing effect, rather than an overall improved training.

Table 13: Perplexity results of RETRO-LI-off with unfrozen GPT-2 backbone.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
RETRO-LI-off	42	43	44	avg	RETRO-LI-off	42	43	44	avg
from ckp	30.16	29.97	24.42	28.18	from ckp	30.61	30.57	26.06	29.08
from scratch	25.69	44.44	22.57	30.90	from scratch	26.30	48.67	23.15	32.71
frozen GPT	55.56	21.60	22.02	33.06	frozen GPT	53.17	22.21	22.59	32.66

Moving on to RETRO-LI-on (2 neighbors, SBERT embeddings) in Table 14, the case is even clearer, namely unfreezing GPT-2 did not improve our language modeling capabilities. This is likely because GPT-2 was trained to a minima of language modeling, so when adding retrieval we only have to train the retrieval parameters. Adding chunked cross-attention changed the loss landscape, which is why unfreezing does not help.

Table 14: Perplexity results of RETRO-LI-on with unfrozen GPT-2 backbone.

(a) Sliding window.					(b) Full results.				
RETRO-LI-on	42	43	44	avg	RETRO-LI-on	42	43	44	avg
from ckp	26.50	27.58	27.81	27.30	from ckp	27.09	28.90	28.48	28.15
from scratch	25.24	37.15	26.87	39.75	from scratch	25.75	42.32	27.62	31.90
frozen GPT	24.26	24.07	23.82	24.05	frozen GPT	24.95	24.84	24.39	24.73

G FAISS Index

G.1 Vector indexes

On the non-parametric side, we need to store document vectors in a manner that facilitates search and optimizes space usage.

Maximum inner product search (MIPS) goes through all the vectors in a database, computes the inner product with the query vector, and returns k vectors with the largest inner product. This is linear in the number of entries of the database, thus entirely impractical for databases consisting of millions or even billions of entries. Performing such a search is recommended only when the quality of the retrieved neighbors is crucial and the search time is less critical.

In order to reduce the search time, we must reduce the search scope. This can be done through locality sensitivity hashing (LSH), which is the method employed by ScaNN. LSH works by hashing the vectors into b buckets, aiming to group similar vectors based on the hash function. Therefore, it might perform sub-optimally if the vectors are poorly distributed. Moreover, it is highly sensitive to the number of buckets b and the hash function.

We can also reduce the scope by adopting an inverted vector files (IVF) approach, like FAISS does. An IVF index clusters the vectors into c centroids, where each vector is assigned to one centroid. Upon receiving a query, we search $nprobe$ of those c cells to find the nearest neighbors. This reduces the search time while preserving good performance. However, an IVF index requires that we train it in order to identify optimal centroids.

Both index types reduce data transfer by decreasing the search scope. In any case, there is a trade-off between search time and result quality. We have established the importance of good neighbors for training a RAG model. Such approximations would not be necessary if the search could be done in memory. This move to an IMC-based platform would lead to the introduction of noise and non-determinism. However, we have demonstrated that any hardware approximate noise is negligible, especially compared to the approximations made by the index itself.

For illustration purposes, we measure the time it takes for the search function call to `IndexIVF_search` to complete and show the results in Table 4. This function is called on 16 chunks concurrently on a Tesla V100 GPU.

G.2 Profiling Details

As a way of profiling the speed of the index calls on FAISS we measure the time it takes for the search function call to `IndexIVF_search` to complete. This function is called on 16 chunks concurrently. We compare three retrieval databases, WikiText-103 with 1'877'559 entries, CNN-DailyMail with 3'488'000 entries, and SlimPajama with 45'107'000 entries. As the number of database entries almost doubles from WikiText-103 to CNN-DailyMail, so does the average search time. Due to the number of database entries, both have an index with 1024 centroids. However, as the number of database entries becomes 12 times larger from CNN-DailyMail to SlimPajama, the number of centroids becomes 4 times larger and the average search time only becomes 6 times longer. The `nprobe` parameter of how many out of the closest centroids to search is set to $\sqrt{n_{centroids}}$.

This emphasizes the role these parameters play in creating the index. Choosing such hyperparameters carefully can be either beneficial or detrimental to the results and speed of the retrieval. It is important to note that naively setting `nprobe` to `ncentroids` would lead to a longer search time than simply searching by brute force.¹⁰

¹⁰ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/faiss/wiki/Faster-search>.

Figure 7: Histograms of search calls on FAISS index for 16 chunks concurrently, on (a) WikiText-103, (b) CNN-DailyMail, and (c) SlimPajama.

H Qualitative Comparison

Up to this point, all the results have been quantitative. To motivate retrieval, especially in domain shift, we now present some qualitative results. We generate the next chunk based on the context. Generation quality metrics such as fluency, diversity, and repetition depend almost exclusively on how well the generator function is written. NVIDIA [34] and DeepMind [2] addressed this by only taking the greedy output. However, for real use cases, it is common to write the generator function with more care, as simple post-processing steps can make a substantial difference in the fluency and the diversity of the generated output.

H.1 Multinomial Generation

The model outputs a $n_{emb} \times n_{vocab}$ matrix which is interpreted as a probability distribution over the vocabulary words. In greedy generation, we take the vocabulary word with the highest probability, but that can lead to significant degeneration, see Figure 11. To generate more natural language, it can be beneficial to occasionally opt for something other than the most likely word.

In multinomial generation, we address this issue with the help of the probability matrix. We cast the matrix as a multinomial distribution and sample from it. This ensures on one hand that it remains likely that we generate words with a higher probability, but also enables us to eventually pick less probable words as well, improving diversity and reducing repetition.

H.2 Top-p Generation

Top-p generation is also called nucleus sampling and aims to address similar issues as multinomial generation. It also helps with diversity of language and repetition, but in this case, the focus is not just on reducing the use of common words, but eliminating them altogether. In nucleus sampling, we set a parameter p describing the cumulative probability. We then remove all tokens in the vocabulary with a cumulative probability above this threshold. This results in a new probability distribution, from which we now sample the next token.

H.3 Results

We generate the next chunks for the best checkpoints and the best-performing validation samples of RETRO-LI-on and -off. We chose the datasets WikiText-103 and SlimPajama, which are the two most extreme cases in terms of perplexity. In order to paint a fuller picture, we present the greedy output, the multinomial and top-p generated results, and the real continuation.

Although there has been tremendous success in evaluating generated samples with GPT-4 (for instance [13] used it and motivated its use by comparing it to human judgment) we had no access to it. GPT-3.5-Turbo rankings of the generated samples are unfortunately not deterministic, and even its evaluation of this handful of qualitative examples rarely aligned with human judgment.

H.3.1 WikiText-103

For WikiText-103 both RETRO-LI-on and -off have the same validation sample with the lowest perplexity, so their continuations can be compared directly. Here we anticipate little difference in the outputs between off and on, as the perplexities are close. Their generated outputs are similar in fluency and comprehensiveness.

Context	Real Continuation Chunk [1.0]	Greedy [0.533]
(...) the ship had an overall length of 425 feet 3 inches (129.6 m), a beam of 75 feet (22.9 m), and a normal draught of 27 feet 3 inches (8.3 m). she displaced 15,200 long tons (15,400 t) at normal load. asahi had a complete double bottom with 55 watertight compartments. her hull was also subdivided into 223 watertight compartments. she was fitted as a flagship and her crew numbered about 773 officers and enlisted men, including the admiral's staff. the ship was powered by two vertical triple - expansion steam engines built by humphrys, tennant, each driving one propeller, using steam generated by 25 belleville boilers at	a working pressure of 17.03 bar (1,703 kpa ; 247 psi). the engines were rated at 15,000 indicated horsepower (11,000 kw), using forced draught, and designed to reach a top speed of 18 knots (33 km	of her earlier- designed battleships. the guns fired a 112.8-pound (50.0 kg) shell at a muzzle velocity of 2,800 ft / s (790 m / s) to a range of approximately 2,500 yards (
	Multinomial [0.449]	Top-p, p=0.9 [0.461]
	of her defence against fast battleship aircraft, mounted in a single main gun turret, high-angle forward, superfiring turrets and armoured casemates. they were backed by krupp armour rather than brick, although the guns could be depressed to - 5 ° and - 2 °. these guns had a	of her designed brautams, as well as four 45-calibre 45-calibre hotchkiss guns, in single turrets. the guns could be depressed to - 5 ° and elevated to + 90 °. they had a maximum elevation of + 35 ° and could be depressed to - 3

Figure 8: RETRO-LI-off generated text for WikiText-103-Validation sample with lowest RETRO-LI-off perplexity.

Context	Real Continuation Chunk [1.0]	Greedy [0.325]
(...) the ship had an overall length of 425 feet 3 inches (129.6 m), a beam of 75 feet (22.9 m), and a normal draught of 27 feet 3 inches (8.3 m). she displaced 15,200 long tons (15,400 t) at normal load. asahi had a complete double bottom with 55 watertight compartments. her hull was also subdivided into 223 watertight compartments. she was fitted as a flagship and her crew numbered about 773 officers and enlisted men, including the admiral's staff. the ship was powered by two vertical triple - expansion steam engines built by humphrys, tennant, each driving one propeller, using steam generated by 25 belleville boilers at	a working pressure of 17.03 bar (1,703 kpa ; 247 psi). the engines were rated at 15,000 indicated horsepower (11,000 kw), using forced draught, and designed to reach a top speed of 18 knots (33 km	of the earlier battleships. her secondary armament consisted of four 12-inch (305 mm) guns mounted in four twin gun turrets, one each fore and aft of the superstructure. the secondary armament was rounded out by five 12-inch (305 mm) guns, each in single mounts
	Multinomial [0.296]	Top-p, p=0.9 [0.430]
	the prominent japanese dreadnought battleships and the remainder of the existing turk gun series of sixteen 20-inch (510 mm) dahlgren guns in a twin -firing gun battery. as hearn 's primary armament, she 's secondary armament was to have consisted	of her keel - class battleships. her secondary battery consisted of six 8-inch (203 mm) guns mounted in casemates in amidships casemates. they fired a 5.5-kilogram (14.9 lb) shell that weighed

Figure 9: RETRO-LI-on generated text for WikiText-103-Validation sample with lowest RETRO-LI-on perplexity.

Context	Real Continuation Chunk [1.0]	Greedy [0.378]
(...) the ship had an overall length of 425 feet 3 inches (129.6 m), a beam of 75 feet (22.9 m), and a normal draught of 27 feet 3 inches (8.3 m). she displaced 15,200 long tons (15,400 t) at normal load. asahi had a complete double bottom with 55 watertight compartments. her hull was also subdivided into 223 watertight compartments. she was fitted as a flagship and her crew numbered about 773 officers and enlisted men, including the admiral's staff. the ship was powered by two vertical triple - expansion steam engines built by humphrys, tennant, each driving one propeller, using steam generated by 25 belleville boilers at	a working pressure of 17.03 bar (1,703 kpa ; 247 psi). the engines were rated at 15,000 indicated horsepower (11,000 kw), using forced draught, and designed to reach a top speed of 18 knots (33 km	of the earlier battleships. her secondary armament consisted of four 12-inch (305 mm) guns mounted in four twin gun turrets, one each fore and aft of the superstructure. the secondary armament was rounded out by five 12-inch (305 mm) guns, each in single mounts
	Multinomial [0.335]	Top-p, p=0.9 [0.363]
	the prominent japanese dreadnought battleships and the remainder of the existing turk gun series of sixteen 20-inch (510 mm) dahlgren guns in a twin -firing gun battery. as hearn 's primary armament, she 's secondary armament was to have consisted	of her keel - class battleships. her secondary battery consisted of six 8-inch (203 mm) guns mounted in casemates in amidships casemates. they fired a 5.5-kilogram (14.9 lb) shell that weighed

Figure 10: RETRO-LI-on trained with a Gaussian regularizer with $\lambda_t = 0.2$, generated text for WikiText-103-Validation sample with lowest RETRO-LI-on perplexity.

H.3.2 SlimPajama

The SlimPajama dataset is by far the worst in terms of perplexity. Though this can easily be addressed with minimal fine-tuning (see Section H.4), we are more interested in true *plug-and-play* performance, as it pertains to retrieval. The question becomes: Can retrieval alone help a language model generalize to unseen domains? In Section 3 we show that this is the case quantitatively, here we analyze the output qualitatively as well. Looking at Figure 11 and Figure 12 side-by-side, we can see the benefit of retrieval. The topic of this excerpt is a description of an HDMI cable. For RETRO-LI-off the generated outputs are vaguely about technology whereas RETRO-LI-on's output is much more on-topic with respect to actual HDMI cables.

To be completely fair, it must be said that this is the best validation sample for RETRO-LI-on, not for RETRO-LI-off.

Context	Real Continuation Chunk [1.0]	Greedy [0.244]
<p>(...) he said besides this the government could give freight subsidy and storage subsidy on the pattern of west bengal and uttar pradesh governments. mr majithia said seed potato could also be exported to pakistan, afghanistan and sri lanka. "if all these steps are are not taken the government alone will be responsible for driving farmers to suicide in despair ", he added.asserting that the state was staring at a farm crisis, the akali leader said potato prices had hit a rock bottom of rs 3 per kilogram. he said in such a situation farmers</p>	<p>were unable to recover the cost of production which came to between rs 6 to rs 8 per kg after adding harvesting and packing costs. "many farmers are even putting off harvesting of their crop due to this reason", he added.the shiromani akali dal (sad) today demanded a relief package of</p>	<p>finger. " the government said that the state was waiting for the state to make a recovery in the famine and that the state 's government had to take the blame for the famine. the government said that the state was waiting for the state to make a recovery in the famine and that the state 's government had</p>
	Multinomial [0.303]	Top-p, p=0.9 [0.403]
	<p>finger.hush ali grandfather : " not only is the state urgent. used alongside high @s securing markets and 232 villages beyond the disaster is the state institutions running in 1979 while there were still the daily abuses which have led to the consumer price abounded. " a convective reference issued in 1978 stated that " people</p>	<p>pubabout. he said before,... then the state government is able to attract customers, prevent famine, preventing corruption and corruption, the government in the future will be able to use this as an excuse for setting up the market in rak being forced by the 2004 withdrawal. " if it doesn 't change it can</p>

Figure 13: RETRO-LI-off generated text for the SlimPajama-6B-Validation sample with the lowest RETRO-LI-off perplexity.

H.4 Fine-tuning

Although our focus so far has been on plug-and-play performance, fine-tuning is straightforward and improves the perplexities drastically with very few samples. We show some results here for minimal fine-tuning, on just one random seed, for our model trained with a Gaussian regularizer, $\lambda_t = 0.2$. We set the number of samples to fine-tune on to 10% of the validation data size, to provide a balanced assessment.

Table 15: Results of fine-tuning on other domains.

Dataset	# Train samples	Train time [min]	Validation perplexity
BBC-News	44	10	65.89
Reuters	17	4	54.37
Atticus contracts	742	6	16.57
Founding docs	1'816	6	48.99
CNN_DailyMail	987	6	39.96
OpenWebText	1'358	4	54.10
SlimPajama	483	5	82.24

Interestingly, neither the initial perplexity nor the number of samples we fine-tune on is an indicator of how well the dataset takes to fine-tuning. Overall, we never have to fine-tune for longer than a few minutes to reach a perplexity of around 40.

BBC-News has been fine-tuned the longest and yet has the second-highest final perplexity. This indicates that either the samples are chosen poorly or our model has trouble with this dataset in particular. Atticus contracts, on the other hand, dropped to a perplexity of around 16, which can be attributed to the repetitive nature of contracts.

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